

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D4.3

MANUAL FOR GOOD PRACTICE AND TRAINING

Summary:

This report presents the key project outputs and demonstrates their practical application. Through in-depth case studies and sector-wide analysis on practices in the extractive sector, key areas have been identified that need further consideration in the sector's sustainability transformation. Additionally, this manual establishes connects between the outputs of SUMEX and the Critical Raw Materials Act, as well as other European requirements, and recommendations on how they can support implementation in the member states.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To establish sustainable management in the extractive sector, practices need to be changed. For this to happen, the sector needs to move away from a purely profit-driven approach to a more societal one and prioritise social and environmental aspects. The aim is to shift beyond legal compliance to a responsible and further sustainable management of mineral raw material extraction. Extractive companies, relevant authorities and civil society are involved in this transformation, as all of them have a different but decisive part in this transformation. Furthermore, the entire value chain of an extraction and production process, and the various mineral products, have to be considered.

This manual summarises the key outputs of the Horizon 2020 project SUMEX (Sustainable Management of Extractive industries) and how they can be applied practically. In this context, SUMEX informs relevant EU and EU member states (MS) policy (e.g. Critical Raw Materials Act) by means of knowledge gathered from in-depth and on the ground case study research as well as a sector-wide analysis of extractive practices. Consequently, SUMEX identifies key areas for corporate and public actors that need further consideration in the sector's sustainability transition.

As a result, permitting, competing land uses and the balance between extraction activities and ecosystem services have been identified as the main challenges for the European extractive industry. The lack of social acceptance towards the extractive sector is an additional factor constraining the expansion of mineral extraction in Europe.

To address the challenges the European extractive sector is currently facing and to facilitate sustainable management in this field, the following points can be highlighted, which require further attention from industry, authority and civil society:

1. Sustainability as dynamic approach
2. Just, inclusive and transformative system change
3. Capacity building as key component
4. Exchange between all actors involved
5. Policy implementation
6. Land-use competition
7. Nature protection vs. exploration and extraction
8. Permitting of new and extension of extraction sites
9. Monitoring and reporting

2 INTRODUCTION

A stable and sustainable supply of mineral resources is crucial for future socio-economic resilience and innovation in the European Union (EU). Due to the site-bound nature of mineral resources, mineral policy has to deal with various factors impacting supply, such as diverse and competing interests of actors and land-use, as well as cross-scale institutional complexity, such as competing or conflicting policy objectives and complex planning procedures. A fundamental requirement for **Europe to remain competitive in global commodity and product markets is to maintain the attractiveness for raw material investments through a fair and straightforward permitting process, while ensuring mineral raw materials production in a socially and environmentally sustainable manner**. The recently presented European Raw Materials Act (European Commission 2023a) is a strong acknowledgement that European policy makers are well aware of these requirements and the role mineral raw materials play in the energy and digital transformations within the European Green Deal (European Commission 2019).

The Horizon 2020 project SUMEX (Sustainable Management in Extractive Industries) is well aligned with the proposed Critical Raw Materials Act (CRMA), as it aims to foster more, but sustainable mineral production within the EU. Improving permitting processes along the extractive value chain (i.e. prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure and post-closure) is a key driver to ensure timely decisions, a transparent state regulatory system, attractive financial and administrative conditions, and sustainable environmental and social conditions. The main mission of the project is to assist policy-makers and other actors on seizing this opportunity.

To promote a sustainable management in the European extractive sector, SUMEX developed a sustainability framework indicating which aspects of sustainability are relevant to address. It does so by considering the **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the European Green Deal and social licence to operate (SLO) criteria**, and by engaging actors from industry, government, academia and civil society from across the EU. The SUMEX Sustainability Framework was then applied **across the entire extractive value chain to analyse minerals, and relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks and industry practices of the EU, member states, selected regions and companies along the project's five focus areas** (presented in Figure 1).

Subsequently, good practices or tools were identified and collected in an open access knowledge repository that is integrated into a broader community of practice (CoP) which forms the basis for capacity building. In addition, a massive open online course (MOOC) has been developed based on the five focus areas, offering a series of webinars and learning materials that also contribute to capacity building and thus knowledge transfer. Both knowledge repository and MOOC consider relevant actor groups, with a focus on permitting authorities and decision makers across the EU.

Figure 1: Overview of the SUMEX project’s key elements – (i) relevant policies and instruments, (ii) focus areas and (iii) extractive value chain life cycle stages

2.1 THE PURPOSE OF THIS MANUAL

This manual is a summary of key outputs of the SUMEX project and demonstrates their practical application. These outputs provide a comprehensive insight of what sustainability means for the extractive sector, as well as concrete examples of how elements or practices of sustainable management can be implemented across the extractive value chain. The focus lies on battery materials, most of which are considered critical raw materials (CRMs), and construction materials. While battery raw materials will play an increasingly important role in the switch to electric vehicles and the energy transition, construction materials are the most important part of Europe’s extractive industry in terms of volume and equally important for our economy. The manual establishes connects between the outputs of SUMEX and the Critical Raw Materials Act, as well as other European requirements, and recommendations on how they can support implementation in the member states.

3 SUSTAINABILITY IN EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRIES

The growing world population, technological advances and the transition to green technology (e.g. energy transition, batteries for electric vehicles) require an increasing amount and diversity of mineral raw materials on the one hand, and the secure and sustainable supply of mineral resources to achieve sustainable development on the other. Technological changes and progress lead to a steady increase in demand for metals in particular in the coming years and decades (European Commission 2020). Some metals, such as cobalt, lithium and rare earths, are crucial in a global context and specifically for Europe, as they are instrumental in the transition to a green economy (European Commission 2019). Subsequently they play a critical role in meeting global and European climate and sustainability targets, such as European Green Deal (European Commission 2019), Paris Agreement (United Nations 2015a), and Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations 2015b). Nevertheless, mining activities in Europe have declined and increasingly been outsourced resulting in intensified import dependencies and supply risks (European Commission 2020; European Union 2020). This trend is reflected in the constantly rising number of mineral raw materials that are classified as critical raw materials by the European Commission (European Commission 2023c).

However, not only metals, also construction minerals are of strategic relevance for Europe. Given their necessity for building infrastructure, as well as due to the quantities extracted, turnover and the number of companies and employees (European Commission 2023b), they have a decisive role for the economy in general and for regional development. In comparison to metal mining, the quarrying of construction minerals is widely spread in Europe, which is partly caused by the availability of deposits in Europe. The large quantities of construction minerals extracted and consumed, and the associated transport costs, are also a determining factor for this trend. Especially in the case of construction minerals, regional supply is significant not only from an economically viable perspective, short transport distances are also preferable from an environmental angle (i.e. less CO₂ emissions).

Generally, Europe has great potential for mining and quarrying. The reasons why this is not being realised are based on various aspects, including competing land uses, strict environmental regulations within the European Union (e.g. CO₂ regulations, protected areas, water directives) or lack of social acceptance. Competing land uses limit the land available for mineral extraction activities, which is conflicting with the domestic security of supply of mineral resources. A key aspect of land use planning is the systematic assessment of potential land use options to foster regional development, secure raw materials supply and at the same time protect natural resources and ecosystems. Some environmental regulations of the European Union, e.g. Natura 2000 and Water Framework Directive (WFD), intensify this land use issue, as they may restrict the land for mineral extraction further to protect environment and biodiversity. In particular, permitting of new or expansion of already existing sites and infrastructure important for extraction (e.g. tailings ponds) are becoming increasingly challenging or even prevented due to this development. But also social aspects contribute to land use conflicts. The lack of social acceptance is a common problem associated with the extraction of non-renewable resources, as it is often perceived as environmentally harmful and socially disadvantageous. Even though the extractive sector's effort to improve environmental and social performance in recent decades, there are still many conflicts present and suspicions towards the extractive sector.

To overcome these conflicts and enhance the social and environmental performance of the extractive sector, sustainable management of the sector is crucial. The pressure to enhance the sustainability performance of the extractive sector, both globally and at European level, has increased enormously in recent decades and years. This development is partly due to the increasing awareness and understanding of the need for and importance of mineral raw materials. In particular Europe has realised an increasing import dependence and supply insecurity, leading to the establishment of initiatives and regulations to address these challenges, such as the Raw Materials Initiative (European Commission 2008) and the Critical Raw Materials Act. Furthermore, several concepts have been developed for the extractive sector which cover elements of a sustainable development approach and aim to drive the extractive sector towards a responsible and sustainable one.

3.1 PROMOTING SUSTAINABILITY IN EXTRACTIVES

One of the key aspects for the sustainability transformation of the extractive sector is knowledge. This implies **industry, as well as policy makers and civil society to gain a better insight and understanding of what sustainability means for the extractive sector and being aware of the opportunities but also limitations.** Depending on the actor group, the requirements and level of knowledge required vary as the influence on the processes differs as well as the area of expertise. In particular for policy makers and industry it is of relevance to have a comprehensive and detailed knowledge of sustainability in the extractive sector, including awareness of what aspects require change and opportunities for improvement. Nevertheless, also civil society needs to be considered in this regard.

For this reason, **the SUMEX project has developed a portfolio of tools and instruments to share knowledge and experience** aimed at a broader target audience to reach various actors with different background knowledge. The main outputs of the project expected to contribute the most to the enhancement of the sectors' sustainability are the SUMEX Sustainability Framework, and the digital toolkit, consisting of the massive open online course (MOOC) and the knowledge repository (see Table 1). In addition, a podcast series "Navigating Challenges & Forging New Paths" has been produced, which describes in six episodes the importance of sustainable management in extractive industries in general and the five focus areas, and is an easy-to-consume medium designed for all actor groups, as well as a set of policy briefs and briefing documents summarising major topics of the project.

Table 1: Brief description and main target audience of the key SUMEX project outputs – also accessible via the project webpage (sumexproject.eu)

Project output	Short description	Main target audience	Link to...
SUMEX Sustainability Framework	Roadmap for the European extractive industry on how to achieve sustainable management within the political framework of the European Green Deal.	Extractive industry & policy	View Framework
Knowledge Repository	Digital platform presenting already existing good sustainable practice example within Europe.	Practitioners in governments & companies	Go to Repository
Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)	Comprehensive online course to share knowledge and build capacity to improve the understanding of what sustainability means for the European extractive sector.	All actor groups	Go to MOOC
SUMEX Podcast	Easy-to-consume medium highlighting the importance of sustainable management in extractives in general in in regard to the five project's focus areas.	All actor groups	Listen here
SUMEX Community of Practice (CoP)	LinkedIn group to share and discuss thoughts, ideas and information in the context of sustainability in the extractive sector.	All actor groups	Access the group

3.2 SUMEX SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

As part of the SUMEX project, the SUMEX Sustainability Framework (see Figure 2) has been developed. This framework goes beyond already existing sustainability approaches for mineral extraction and is a result of a multi-stakeholder process.

Although the framework is targeted at the European extractive sector, it can also be applied as a global guide. **The SUMEX Sustainability Framework serves as roadmap to move from compliance with legal requirements to responsibility and further to sustainable management in the extractive sector.** In doing so, environmental, social and economic aspects relevant to the extractive industry are taken into account by structuring the framework in three dimensions, namely (i) environmental sustainability, (ii) social and societal responsibility, and (iii) transforming the economy.

Each dimension contains **aspects describing key areas of sustainable management in the extractive industries**, reflecting the ambitions of the European Green Deal to transform the European economy into an inclusive, circular and carbon-neutral system by 2050. To achieve this, the sustainability aspects defined in the framework require implementation of processes. These aspects cover a range of topics (e.g. valuing social and natural capital, planning beyond the mine life) and targets (e.g. no bribes, zero greenhouse gas emissions). The topics that should be considered in the context of responsible and sustainable mineral extraction have a temporal context, i.e. some of them need to be addressed in the present (e.g. emergency preparedness and risk management, diversity and anti-discrimination) and others are future-oriented (e.g. defining the role of extractives in a green economy, carbon neutrality).

Figure 2: SUMEX Sustainability Framework ([click here](#) for better view)

3.3 LEVERAGE POINTS

The conceptual model of Leverage Points (LPs), developed by Donella Meadows (Meadows 1999), provides a **tool and lens for evaluating sustainability interventions and ‘sustainable management’ measures** on their potential to initiate change at different levels in a (sub)system, as well as assessing the different impacts. LPs are points in the respective system where even small changes can bring about significant changes and thus refer to system change processes in which a system reorganises itself (e.g. towards sustainability), resulting in a new state. Therefore, these are **change processes that affect technologies, rules, structural change, attitudes, values and behaviours or knowledge and information flows**.

Leverage points can occur singly or as chains or cascades, acting at different points in the system individually and/or sequentially, simultaneously or across different scales, policy areas and time periods. Meadows suggests a **hierarchy of twelve LPs, from shallow (i.e. incremental changes with little impact on changing a system) to deeper (i.e. transformative and disruptive)**. Shallow leverage points cover elements such as buffers, stocks and flows, or feedback loops, while deep leverage points cover information flow, institutions and structural components, the goal of a system, and its underlying paradigm and values. Furthermore, these twelve LPs can be grouped into four main categories that resemble the characteristics of the core system (see Table 2): parameters, feedback, design, and intent. Interventions at different LPs should not be seen as competing with each other, rather as complementing each other. **Shallow LP interventions and measures are popular with policy makers and managers. In contrast, deep LPs are difficult to target and change because they are beyond traditional political election cycles and require societal paradigm shifts that are difficult to achieve through political and regulatory mechanisms alone.** Figure 3 presents the leverage points approach developed for the extractive sector (for more information see [‘SD Criteria – SUMEX Sustainability Framework’](#)).

Table 2: Leverage Points describing the four main characteristics of a system (source '[SD Criteria – SUMEX Sustainability Framework](#)')

System Characteristics		Leverage Points		
Parameter	Modifiable, mechanistic characteristic (e.g. taxes, incentives and standards, or physical elements such as size of stocks or material flows); those are the ones typically addressed by policy makers	12	Parameters	Shallow Leverage Points
		11	Size of buffer stocks, relative to their flows	
		10	Material stocks and flows, e.g. transport and infrastructure	
Feedback	Interactions between elements that impact the internal dynamics of a system or that provide information regarding desired outcomes	9	Lengths of delays, relative to the rate of a system change	
		8	Strengths of balancing feedback loops, relative to the impacts they are trying to correct against	
		7	Gain around positive, reinforcing feedback loops	
Design	Characteristics that relate to the core structure of a system: rules, power and self-organisation; social structures and institutions that manage feedback and parameters	6	Structure of information flows and the access to information (who does and does not have access to information)	Deep Leverage Points
		5	Rules and institutions that build the structure of the system	
		4	Power to add, change or self-organise the system structure	
Intent	Underpinning value, attitudes, goals and/or worldviews of actors and stakeholders that shape the direction of a system, the other three characteristics are directed towards the intent	3	Goals of the system	
		2	Mindset, paradigms and underpinning worldviews in which the system is rooting	
		1	Power to transcend paradigms	

Figure 3: Leverage Points Perspective adapted to the subsystem of the extractive industries (source '[SD Criteria – SUMEX Sustainability Framework](#)')

4 CHANGING PRACTICES

To foster sustainability in the extractive sector **and ensure a socially and environmentally compatible mineral raw materials activities**, practices need to be changed. Although the sector's performance has improved in recent decades and years, especially in the European extractive industry, the potential and need for progress remain high. The aim is to **shift from compliance with legal requirements, to responsible management in the extractive sector and further to sustainable management**. This presumes considering the entire extractive value chain, i.e. access and exploration, extraction and processing, as well as closure and post-closure. Each life cycle stage of an extraction site contains different opportunities but also challenges that has to be considered accordingly. In addition to a life-cycle approach, the SUMEX project addresses five focus areas – i.e. land use planning, permitting, socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, health and safety, and reporting. These areas are key topics in the sustainability transformation of an extraction site, as each has a certain impact on the design and implementation of mineral extraction. The **permitting process of an extraction site has a special value in implementing sustainable practices**, as in this stage, the extraction, as well as the closure and post-closure phases are determined and planned. Impact assessment is typically part of the permitting process to **ensure environmentally and socially sound extraction activities**.

The implementation of sustainable practices in an existing extraction site is often more complex, as on the one hand changes to existing operations have economic consequences and on the other hand they have to be approved by authorities, meaning impact assessment for the adopted operation may have to be performed again. Nevertheless, the introduction of sustainable practices into current operations is important to protect as well as provide benefits to environment and society. This covers environmental, social and economic aspects (see SUMEX Sustainability Framework), including resource efficiency, workers wellbeing, promotion of regional development, etc. Whereas the **extraction phase causes impacts that need to be prevented and at least minimised as far as possible through sustainable management**, the closure and post-closure stage entails the possibility of creating a positive legacy. In addition to ensuring safety (i.e. stability, protection from rockfall, tailings, etc.), the focus is on the meaningful transformation of the post-extractive landscape that has a positive impact, i.e. enhancing biodiversity.

4.1 GOOD PRACTICES

With the ambition to introduce sustainable management throughout the entire extractive value chain, the SUMEX project has developed a collection of EU industry and policy good sustainable practices – the SUMEX knowledge repository. This data collection aims to support the transition to a sustainable extractive sector by demonstrating already existing good sustainable practices that can be implemented into the processes of the extractive value chain. It is intended to facilitate the integration of sustainable practice into extractive operations, as well as their assessment by decision-makers, as the impact of these practices are already known.

For the development of the knowledge repository, a comprehensive screening of EU relevant research projects (i.e. Horizon 2020, EIT RawMaterials, European Regional Development Fund, and European Social and Cohesion Fund), as well as national and regional level projects, and industry guidance and practices (e.g. AngloAmerican, Boliden, ICMM, KGHM, LKAB, RioTinto, and UEPG) has been conducted (see report '[Inventory of relevant](#)

[extractive projects](#)). The identification of good sustainable practices for the extractive industry in both business and public sector is based on the taxonomy including a series of methodologies and frameworks, described in more detail in the report '[Analytical framework](#)'. Furthermore, the sustainability aspects listed in the SUMEX Sustainability Framework, as well as the five focus areas of the project, are relevant to the identification process. To verify both the accuracy of the mapping and the relevance of the identified practices to the project's objectives, a quality control mechanism has been introduced.

SUMEX defines good sustainable practices as those practices for the extractive industry that initiate learning and change, i.e. practices that have the potential to drive the shift towards a sustainable extractive sector. Implementing such practices in the extractive value chain are expected to have a positive impact on economic, environmental and/or social aspects. Currently, the SUMEX knowledge repository contains 370 good sustainable practices. However, external contributors have the possibility to provide practices, which are reviewed by experts and added to the repository if they meet the criteria, i.e. it is a dynamic tool geared to grow continually.

4.1.1 GOOD PRACTICE CRITERIA

The relevance of the practices in the repository is classified by different descriptive criteria (listed in Table 3) representing the SUMEX approach to sustainability (see SUMEX reports '[European Sustainable Development Framework](#)' and '[SD Criteria - SUMEX Sustainability Framework](#)'). These criteria indicate what the practice is about, for which target audience it is relevant or what impact its implementation might have.

Table 3: Overview of the descriptive criteria used for the SUMEX knowledge repository

Descriptive criteria	Overview
Sustainability Scope	With the development of the SUMEX Sustainability Framework, a set of objectives and thematic areas have been defined with the goal of transitioning the European extractive sector towards a sustainable one. Although the sub-topics within the framework's sustainability dimensions (i.e. environmental, social and societal, and economic) are specific, a practice can also encompass multiple sub-topics from different dimensions, since many practices follow broad-based approach.
Focus Areas	The SUMEX focus areas (i.e. socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, reporting official statistics, land use planning, health and safety, and permitting process/policy integration) represent the key topics of the sustainability transition of the European extractive sector. These focus areas not only overlap but also complete each other, offering a holistic approach. Due to the overlapping characteristic of the focus areas, a single practice can also belong to several focus areas.

<p>Life Cycle Stage</p>	<p>Each phase of the extractive value chain brings different opportunities but also challenges in the context of sustainability. The repository, distinguished following five life cycle stages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-exploration (land-use planning) • Exploration • Pre-exploitation/development stage (e.g. feasibility study) • Exploitation • Post-exploitation (i.e. rehabilitation)
<p>Commodity Type</p>	<p>In the context of sustainable management, the type of raw material extracted is mainly relevant in particular life cycle stages, e.g. mineral processing, or situations, e.g. promotion of CRMs extraction. For this reason, despite the specificity of the raw material, practices are often applicable for any commodity type. Nevertheless, the repository differs between construction minerals (i.e. aggregates), industrial minerals, as well as metalliferous and non-metalliferous minerals, with the project's focus on battery and construction materials.</p>
<p>Practice Type</p>	<p>Both industry and policy-makers play crucial roles in achieving sustainable management in the extractive sector. The industry is responsible for integrating sustainable practices into the extractive site life cycle stages, while policy-makers are in charge of requiring and/or permitting the implementation of practices (e.g. integration in legislation, improvement of regulatory framework). Therefore, the repository contains practices that aim to support the industry in improving its performance (i.e. industry practices), and those referring to legal requirements to promote the sector's sustainability performance (i.e. public policy practices).</p>
<p>Data Item Type</p>	<p>Sustainability transformation in the extractive industry requires the implementation of sustainable practices across the extractive value chain, as well as also the provision of knowledge to improve processes. A good sustainable practice comprises impact, guidance and informing decision-making, i.e. a concrete instrument, tool, service or product to support actions and decision-making processes, resulting in practice or knowledge base. While practice base is an action practice which can be tangibly implemented, knowledge base facilitates to implement practices.</p>
<p>Format Type</p>	<p>The format type depends on the type of the practice and the target audience the practice is intended for. They can vary in terms of characteristics such as information content (e.g. technical data), scope (e.g. level of details) and access to information (e.g. public availability). The repository classifies into the following format types:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy brief • Report/document • Repository, resource libraries & toolkits • Website

<p>Learning Relevance</p>	<p>In addition to the format type and data item type, the target audience needs to know how the data can be used for knowledge transfer. This means, whether the practice is a concrete practical example (i.e. case study), a guide (i.e. guideline/guidance document, handbook or tool(kit)), or learning material (i.e. course or training materials, MOOC, webinar).</p>
<p>System Change Potential</p>	<p>The concept of leverage points provides a model to introduce system change potential with varying degrees of impact, i.e. ranging from shallow (incremental change with minor leverage on changing system) to deep (transformative and disruptive). It identifies specific points within a system or subsystem where changes can cause shifts within that system. Transformative change requires new or modified practices at various intervention points, including technology, rules and institutions, information flow, and attitudes, values and behaviours.</p>

4.2 GOOD PRACTICES' SUSTAINABILITY SCOPE

The sustainability scope of a good sustainable practice refers to the SUMEX Sustainability Framework and its underlying goals and thematic areas, i.e. sustainability aspects of the three dimensions - environmental sustainability, socio- and societal responsibility, and transforming the economy. Improving the environmental and social performance of the extractive sector is crucial to promote sustainability in mineral extraction and is frequently emphasised. However, the consideration of economic factors also plays a relevant role, with the aim of achieving a systemic change that is in line with the objectives of the European Green Deal.

The practices of the SUMEX knowledge repository typically include multiple sustainability aspects, often covering several dimensions. According to the analysis of the data collection, the economic dimension is considered by the majority of the practices (i.e. 311 practices, 84% overall), followed by social and societal (i.e. 250, 68%), and environmental dimension (i.e. 211, 57%), as presented in Figure 4. This indicates that the economic system change, which has become an important issue due to some critical topics (e.g. growing supply risk of certain raw materials), is also reflected in the sustainability transformation of the European extractive sector.

Figure 4: Number of good practices related to each sustainability dimension

4.2.1 ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

The biophysical boundaries of our planet are limits that should not be crossed. Mankind and its (economic) activities, which include the extraction of mineral resources, should operate within a frame that respects these limitations. As the extraction of minerals has many impacts on the environment and thus the planetary boundaries, the sector needs to identify pathways to significantly reduce these impacts, i.e. towards zero, or even create positive effects. Water and energy consumption, land use, air emissions and waste generation are aspects of mineral extraction and processing that have a strong impact on the environment and therefore need to be addressed accordingly.

Integrated, watershed-based water stewardship, i.e. a comprehensive and jointly planned management of all water systems, both company internal and external, is intended to address the large amounts of water required by the extractive sector. The focus is on water used as valued resource, water efficiency, and the avoidance of freshwater use (European Commission 2019), as well as the creation of a flexible, resilient water infrastructure that can respond to different scenarios. To optimise energy efficiency of mineral extraction and processing, companies need continuously improve and innovate their processes. Additionally, the achievement of carbon neutrality requires energy consumption predominantly sourced from renewable energies. Harmful air emissions of the extractive sector have to be reduced to zero by optimising processes, directly and indirectly related to extraction and processing activities. Biodiversity and ecosystem services are affected by the use of land for mineral extraction. The optimal use of land in a spatial and temporal context, i.e. before, during and after the extraction phase, requires the cooperation of all actors involved in land use. The negative impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services have to be addressed in particular in a way to reduce them to a minimum and turn them from being negative towards net positive. Potential indirect impacts, i.e. industrial activities associated with extractive industries, are included. The transition to a circular economy requires a waste management system, including secondary resources from traditional waste by-products (e.g. waste rock and tailings), continuous reduction of waste generated and the treatment and/or storage of waste without the need for landfilling and impacts on the environment.

The mapping of good practices for the extractive industry identified examples on all aspects deemed relevant for environmental sustainability according to the SUMEX Sustainability Framework. Figure 5 clearly shows that land-use planning and biodiversity are the most addressed topics with 120 good practices (37%) compared to the other aspects of this sustainability dimension. Reason for this is the great attention paid to the conservation of ecosystem services and biodiversity in recent years, which is directly linked to changing land-uses, and competing land uses, which is also a critical issue in Europe caused by increasing land sealing. Almost 25% (90) of the good practices dealing with waste management. Circular economy has become an increasingly important topic in Europe, and thus also for the extractive sector, among others due to the awareness that the demand for mineral raw materials cannot be met by primary resources alone and the need for land for tailings management.

Even though water stewardship is a more specific topic, it comprises 17% of the examples in the knowledge repository. The adoption and implementation of the Water Framework Directive in EU countries and the associated regulations and requirements have led to water (i.e. consumption and impact of water bodies by extraction activities) becoming an increasingly challenging aspect for the extractive sector. The sustainability aspects air emissions, carbon neutrality and effective energy consumption seems to be considered less, only between 10% (37 good practices) and 8% (31 and 30 practices). Nevertheless, these thematic areas are of high relevance for the extractive sector and need further research of how to improving them. For instance, the aim of carbon neutrality is part of the EU climate targets and the achievement of the European Green Deal.

Figure 5: Number of good practices related to each ‘Environmental sustainability’ aspect

4.2.2 SOCIAL AND SOCIETAL RESPONSIBILITY

Different views on mineral extraction have an impact on extractive projects. Social acceptance is a crucial topic, as its absence may hamper or even cause projects to fail. For this reason, the involvement of all actors, whether they are affected by the operation (i.e. local community) or not (i.e. wider society), is essential and contributes to fostering social acceptance. Defining and implementing a shared vision of the future requires active collaboration between companies and society. This includes continuous engagement, procedural and deliberative justice, and opportunities to actively participate in the process and take an active role in decision-making. Furthermore, it requires trustworthy grievance mechanisms and shared investigation and problem-solving processes so that actors can raise critical questions, concerns and complaints without hesitation.

With the aim of gaining trust, data and information need to be shared with actors transparently and in a timely manner, including payments and revenues, and data regarding environmental, health and safety performance of the company's operation. Extractive companies adhere to ethical corporate practices, which include neither supporting nor tolerating corruption and bribery. Human rights (e.g. free and prior informed consent) and cultural heritage (including indigenous peoples) must be respected and protected. Furthermore, diversity and inclusion are promoted, while discrimination is eliminated; referring to factors such as gender, age, skin colour and origin of the persons involved in the funding project, indigenous peoples and different cultural or religious groups.

The well-being of employees in the company is of fundamental importance, meaning that continuous efforts are made by companies to ensure and improve working conditions. Zero-harm culture, health and safety and fair compensation are seen as the base. It also involves analysing the continuous improvement of skills and the involvement of workers in company processes, i.e. a culture of continuous learning and collaboration with social actors to envisage the whole picture of a site, company or sector or its products embedded in an ever-changing society and environment. Further, there is a need for reflexivity and reflection on a form of learning in terms of a jointly developed vision and values that guide a theory of action for particular practices.

All SUMEX sustainability aspects relating to social and societal responsibility are reflected by the knowledge repository. The focus of practices in this sustainability dimension is on holistic management and continuous learning (31%), as well as aspects related to information disclosure and community engagement (see Figure 6). Emphasis on transparency, stakeholder engagement and shared vision partnership (each between 26 & 28%), underline the importance of both passive and active involvement of society for the extractive industry. However, the knowledge repository contains only a few practices on cultural heritage and FPIC (11%), and ethical practices (10%), what might be due to the fact that these topics are very specific and linked to regions, e.g. Sami community in northern Europe. Nonetheless, they still require further investigation to align mineral extraction with the rights of indigenous communities and ethical practices. Workers well-being (15%), diversity, inclusion and anti-discrimination (7%) and human rights (5%) are also addressed in very few practices. The standard in European extraction sites is already advanced compared to other areas, which means that these sustainability aspects are no longer major issues in Europe. Nevertheless, these aspects should not be neglected and requires constant assessment and improvement.

Figure 6: Number of good practices related to each ‘Social and societal responsibility’ aspect

4.2.3 TRANSFORMING THE ECONOMY (I.E. CONSIDERING THE GREEN DEAL)

Extractives have an essential role in achieving the goals of the European Green Deal, which intends to transform the European Union’s economy towards a green, circular and inclusive one (“leaving no person behind”), as they are basic requirement for the transition. Therefore, the extractive sector needs to understand its role in this transition (e.g. which raw materials are crucial, which not), how to measure this role with indicators and what types of improved and innovative technologies and new/modified business models will be required. It also needs to deal with changing consumption patterns (i.e. usage instead of ownership) and considerations of needs, e.g. role of mineral raw materials for producing luxury items in such an economy.

Key aspects for this transition are closed cycles with highly increased material efficiencies, reduced dependency on imports of minerals overall and from irresponsible sourcing practices, and a demand that can be partly covered by secondary sources. Different loops like sharing, prolonging, remanufacturing and recycling will be crucial. As a result, circularity will significantly impact the extractive sector far beyond recycling, emphasising reduction/dematerialisation, multiple use and redesign of products. Waste products can be re-used as a secondary product for other industrial processes (e.g. full value extraction), implying also closer linkages to other parts of the economy/avoiding enclaves. The sector will be required to examine life-cycle considerations regarding its products and product labelling and will be accountable for them.

Knowledge of the value of natural capital (e.g. biodiversity and ecosystem services) and social capital (e.g. relationships and networks between individuals and groups and the resulting ability to secure or maintain skills, resources, knowledge or information) is both monetary and includes ethical, moral or cultural ("values") dimensions that facilitate their inclusion in accounting and reporting systems and decision-making processes and enable appropriate consideration of natural and social capital. For natural capital in particular, this knowledge is important for conducting an adequate appraisal of services and benefits to either guarantee its restoration or its continued existence and sustainable use. As extractive industries have the potential to generate significant benefits, it is important to define what benefit sharing means in the context of a shared vision for the future, addressing all dimensions of value, i.e. beyond the payment of taxes and job creation. The question is how these benefits can and should be shared between stakeholders, i.e. since the current "social contract - jobs vs. environmental impacts" will change with ongoing automatisations in the near future.

All these aspects are of relevance for planning beyond the site's life from the very beginning when planning, to ensure the company has budgeted for the post-extraction phase and considered the full range of social and environmental aspects. This includes the closure phase, required socio-economic transitions to enable succeeding activities/livelihoods and the subsequent land-use. The same applies to risk management, where the extractive sector needs to exert a holistic approach towards risks and opportunities related to this transformation, but it also needs to increase its emergency preparedness to prevent events with catastrophic consequences going forward.

Also for this sustainability dimension, good practices were identified for all aspects of the SUMEX framework. The sustainability aspect 'planning beyond the mine life' was most widely covered in the repository with 40%, while 'valuing all forms of capital' was among the least popular aspects with 6%. Post-closure planning has gained significance for industry, politics and social society due to the growing awareness of the importance of responsible and sustainable post-extraction landscape design. This has led to more consideration being given to post-closure planning, which is also reflected in the number of practices. The low number of practices on capital valuation is due to the fact that the question on how to value natural and social capital is complex and there is not yet a clear methodology that industry and policy-makers might use as a basis for this evaluation. The sustainability aspect of accountability is also discussed in a large number of practices (33%), mainly as a result of the growing demand for it from both legal and societal perspectives. The same applies to benefit sharing (19% of practices), associated with the social component, or more precisely, social acceptance. To render mineral extraction socially acceptable, it is crucial, among other things, that society has an added value, i.e. that regional and socio-economic development is enhanced by extraction activities. Holistic risk management and emergency preparedness, reflected by 20% of the practices in the repository, is also linked to social and societal responsibility and part of the focus area health and safety, as it includes the safety of workers and society. Europe is already at a higher level in this area, but regular assessment and improvement is relevant to avoid losing ground. The role and indicators of the extractive sector in a closed loop and for an inclusive green economy are part of the European Union's climate policy, i.e. European Green Deal. The practices on these topics represent only 12% and 13% of the knowledge repository, as both have only recently gained attention and are therefore not yet integrated across a wide range of the extraction sector. Moreover, the implementation of these aspects poses a certain challenge for the sector, as they are connected to political and societal factors, such as the permitting of relevant facilities or system change.

Figure 7: Number of good practices related to each 'Transforming the economy' aspect

4.3 SUMEX FOCUS AREA CONSIDERATION

The five focus areas have been identified by the European Commission as those areas that require the most attention in the context of the transition towards sustainability in the European extractive sector. The SUMEX knowledge repository is based on the focus areas as a decisive criterion for the selection of good sustainable practices for the extractive sector. However, it should be noted that some of the focus areas need greater emphasis than others: There has already been significant progress in the area of health and safety in recent decades, making it a less pressing issue nowadays. In contrast, the thematic area 'Permitting process/policy integration' has become increasingly relevant due to various factors, such as the ever-growing regulatory framework and land-use conflicts. Analysing the knowledge repository reveals an overarching priority of the focus area 'Socio-economic and environmental impact assessment', while the other focus areas are largely on the same level (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Number of good practices assigned to each SUMEX focus area (370 practices in total)

4.3.1 SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT

With 71% of the practices (264 out of 370) including aspects related to impact assessment, the importance of evaluating the implications of activities across the extractive value chain is underlined. The overall objective of assessing the impact of mineral raw material activities is to prevent or at least reduce negative impacts, and to generate and promote positive ones by identifying the potential consequences. To promote environmental and social sustainability, regulatory frames that are implemented by authorities, as well as a range of initiatives and company frameworks have been established. Typically impact assessment is part of the regulatory and permitting system, which emphasises the importance of design characteristics of an extraction site.

The focus of good sustainable practices included in the knowledge repository that belong to this category is on extraction site life cycle stages of exploitation and post-exploitation (i.e. rehabilitation), as indicated in Table 4. This emphasis results from the impacts and conflicts these two life cycle stages can cause, both environmentally and socially. These include environmental consequences such as the destruction of ecosystems and the reduction of biodiversity, and social considerations such as the lack of social acceptance and negative consequences on the surrounding community due to mineral extraction, e.g. dust or noise.

Table 4: Distribution of good practices on impact assessment across the life cycle stages

SUMEX focus area	Number of practices	Life cycle stage	Number of practices
Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments	264	Pre-exploration (land-use planning)	106 (40%)
		Exploration	109 (41%)
		Pre-exploitation / development stage (e.g. feasibility study)	128 (48%)
		Exploitation phase	188 (71%)
		Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	192 (73%)
		Assigned to all life cycle stages	81 (31%)

Given the number of good sustainable practices on impact assessment recorded in the knowledge repository in general and in relation to the individual life cycle stages, it can be concluded that this focus area is already being addressed intensively, and has been well integrated and adapted into the current system. Especially in the post-exploitation phase, the combination of the focus areas impact assessment and land-use planning is essential, as demonstrated in the good practice example blow (see Figure 9). Ecological restoration of a post-extraction landscape, combined with effective land use planning, ensures a meaningful use. Furthermore, the example points out that a communication system with the community, public participation and the provision of an added value for the community (in this case in the form of a training and leisure facility), constitute an integral part of the post-extraction decision-making phase.

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COMMUNITY-BASED ENVIRONMENTAL RESTORATION

- Health and safety
- Land-use planning
- Permitting processes / policy integration
- Reporting official statistics
- Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments

Challenge the practice is addressing: This practice addresses the community-based environmental restoration in Dambovită, Romania. The Fusea site, located in the floodplain of the Argeș river is a mixed area of economical and natural value. With direct involvement of the Lafarge team, this site provides a good chance to demonstrate the importance of ecological restoration of degraded floodplains and to provide a community-based system of administering the area's environmental services. The project also includes a significant communication component for community participation as well as the establishment of training and leisure facilities for a broader audience.

Concrete practice to achieve the expected goal: The project included two phases: With a two-year duration, the initial phase of the project focused on the start-up of the community involvement process as well as the technical work setting up the restoration measures for the area. The second phase included greater combined company and community activity to manage the site's human activities while also promoting the Fusea Natural Area as a best practice model for Lafarge employees, ecologists, mining specialists, and the general public.

Expected impact/goal of the practice: As a result, with the direct involvement of the Lafarge team, this site provides a good chance to demonstrate the importance of ecological restoration of degraded floodplains and to provide a community-based system of administering the area's environmental services.

Who is the target user group of the practice/intervention or implementing the practice/intervention? This practice is relevant for both public policy and industry contexts.

HYPERLINK View document

SOURCE
WATER MANAGEMENT CASE STUDY (p. 1)

DATA ITEM TYPE
Practice base

PRACTICE TYPE
Industry
Public policy

FORMAT
Report / document

LEARNING RELEVANCE
Case study

COMMODITY
Unspecified (universally applicable)

EXTRACTIVE LIFE-CYCLE
Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)

SUSTAINABILITY SCOPE
Planning beyond the mine life
Benefit sharing
Stakeholder engagement
Shared vision partnerships
Water stewardship
Land-use and biodiversity

SYSTEM CHANGE POTENTIAL
ecological restoration of degraded floodplains
community-based environmental restoration

Figure 9: Good practice example on impact assessment ([click here](#) to see the example in the repository)

4.3.2 REPORTING

Aspects of reporting covers only 29% (107) of the practices. Reporting provides an instrument for companies to strengthen and internalise their commitment to sustainable development, as it allows them to tracking their economic, environmental and social performance. In addition, reporting can be used for communication with external actors by publishing them. The public dissemination of reports and disclosure of company internal (exclusive confidential information) demonstrates transparency. Thus, this has the potential to positively impact the company, e.g. enhancing social acceptance or facilitating a two-way exchange of information. As reporting is typically undertaken by industry actors, the lack of involvement of independent auditors or affected actors (e.g. municipalities, NGO representatives) may be criticised.

Table 5 highlights similar numbers of reporting practices across the extractive life cycle stages. The majority of good sustainable practices in the context of reporting involve the implementation of corporate protocols, guidelines and tools for monitoring and evaluating processes at the site level.

Table 5: Distribution of good practices on reporting across the life cycle stages

SUMEX focus area	Number of practices	Life cycle stage	Number of practices
Reporting	107	Pre-exploration (land-use planning)	67 (63%)
		Exploration	60 (56%)
		Pre-exploitation / development stage (e.g. feasibility study)	63 (59%)
		Exploitation phase	76 (71%)
		Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	69 (64%)
		Assigned to all life cycle stages	45 (42%)

Reporting is closely linked to a range of other areas of mineral extraction activities, i.e. life cycle stages and focus areas, as monitoring is an integral part. The good practice example on reporting shown here (see Figure 10) exemplifies the interaction between the focus areas of reporting, permitting and land-use planning, whereby the disclosure of information and data to other relevant actors is at the centre of the good practice. Through the disclosure of high quality geological information from geological surveys to industry and authorities, exploration and exploitation projects are promoted and thus raw materials production within Europe strengthened.

Figure 10: Good practice example on reporting ([click here](#) to visit the example in the repository)

4.3.3 LAND-USE PLANNING

The rate of good sustainable practices identified for land use planning lies at 29%. Extraction activities require land, making land use a relevant issue at every stage of the extractive life cycle. Land-use is a challenging issue given to different interests of various actors and resulting competing land-uses, as well as numerous development pressures. The role of land-use planning and governance is to regulate land-use, balance the different interests and ensure sustainable use that respects ecological limitations. Effective land-use planning needs to provide access to resources while complying with environmental and social aspects of sustainability.

69% and 68% of the land-use planning practices respectively are allocated to the exploitation and post-exploitation phase of an extraction site (see Table 6). The life cycle phase of pre-exploration, which is basically specific to land-use planning, accounts for 53% of the good sustainable practices of this focus area. In the exploitation phase, land use planning is in principle no longer a major issue, as the decision has already been made to use the land for the extraction of mineral raw materials. However, this often involves the expansion of the extraction site or land-use conflicts due to already existing extraction sites, as well as the mitigation of spatial-environmental impacts of extraction activities such as land sealing through the infrastructure of the

extraction site and impacts on land intensity. The post-exploitation phase is an important issue in land-use planning, as it is concerned with transforming the land into a different use. There are many options for transforming the extraction site into a post-extraction landscape. The challenge is to balance this transformation with the needs of the various actors and environmental sustainability. Many of the land-use practices in the knowledge repository deal with topics such as decision-making support, public policy (e.g. access to raw materials) and other land-use policy instruments (e.g. financial incentives, financing, subsidies), as well as standards for regulating land-use or the subsequent use of extraction sites.

Table 6: Distribution of good practices on land-use planning across the life cycle stages

SUMEX focus area	Number of practices	Life cycle stage	Number of practices
Land-use planning	103	Pre-exploration (land-use planning)	55 (53%)
		Exploration	40 (39%)
		Pre-exploitation / development stage (e.g. feasibility study)	38 (37%)
		Exploitation phase	69 (67%)
		Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	68 (66%)
		Assigned to all life cycle stages	22 (21%)

The integration of extraction activities into land-use planning is has the potential to support the mitigation of conflicts over competing land uses and to secure the safeguarding of raw materials. Especially the supply of aggregates poses a challenge in terms of land-use planning, as this group of raw materials is usually extracted close to the consumer due to its large volume and low value (i.e. short transport distances). Following the extraction of construction materials is widespread in Europe, compared to metal production. Integrating land evaluation into land-use planning policies can achieve a number of benefits at the policy level in terms of decision-making and implementation of regulations, as the good practice example in Figure 11 reveals. This includes the simplification of extraction and environmental permitting procedures, the development of efficient extraction and environmental land-use planning in line with national plans, and the improvement of decision-making processes in the context of facing the challenge of competing land uses, i.e. balancing environmental sensitivity to mineral extraction with the potential for development of extraction activities.

Figure 11: Good practice example on land-use planning ([click here](#) to visit the example in the repository)

4.3.4 HEALTH AND SAFETY

27% of the practices contained in the knowledge repository, i.e. 99, are dealing with the focus area health and safety. Both aspects inside and outside the extractive operation are part of health and safety considerations. Occupational safety, i.e. the safety, health and well-being of people involved in the extractive life cycle, and process safety, i.e. the prevention of extraction-related incidents such as tailings dam failures, fires or roof support system collapses, have a high priority. However, the well-being of individuals and communities in the vicinity of the extraction site needs to be addressed through appropriate measures.

The analysis of the data repository indicates that a large share of the 'health and safety'-practices concern the exploitation phase (presented in Table 7). The exploration phase is the main part of resource extraction and involves the most work that might have negative health and safety impacts on the people working in the operation but also on others. Therefore, measures to improve occupational and process safety, as well as the well-being of workers and communities are particularly relevant at this life cycle stage and consequently need to be continuously assessed and improved. Practices in this focus areas concerning post-exploitation phases represent the second largest share. They cover aspects such as the safety of extractive infrastructures, which are still in place after the extraction site closed and might pose potential risks for its surroundings (e.g. dam failure). Potential contamination of water or soil that have to be prevented or at least mitigated is also to consider at this stage of a site's life cycle.

Table 7: Distribution of good practices on health and safety across the life cycle stages

SUMEX focus area	Number of practices	Life cycle stage	Number of practices
Health and safety	99	Pre-exploration (land-use planning)	29 (29%)
		Exploration	35 (35%)
		Pre-exploitation / development stage (e.g. feasibility study)	53 (54%)
		Exploitation phase	88 (89%)
		Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	67 (68%)
		Assigned to all life cycle stages	28 (28%)

Health and safety are principally no longer a major issue in European extraction sites, due to the progress that has been made in the last decades and the decrease of accidents that can be traced back to occupational health and safety measures. Nevertheless, appropriate precautions need to be taken continuously to prevent hazards and to respond effectively in the event of an accident. In its Emergency Preparedness and Response Planning section (see good practice example, Figure 12), AngloAmerican has defined a guideline for the prevention and management of potential emergencies at extraction sites. The guideline’s priority is to prevent incidents by implementing appropriate measures. Second, it aims to introduce adequate processes to deal with any emergencies that may occur to minimise consequences as far as possible.

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EMERGENCY PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE PLANNING

- Health and safety ●
- Land-use planning ●
- Permitting processes / policy integration ●
- Reporting official statistics ●
- Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments ●

Challenge the practice is addressing: AngloAmerican’s Emergency Preparedness and Response Planning section provides guidance on how to prevent and deal with possible emergencies on mining sites. The aim of this guidance is to minimise dangerous situations in operations and to protect workers from accidents.

Concrete practice to achieve the expected goal: Emergency Preparedness and Response planning apply to the whole mining life cycle. According to the planning and operationalisation guidance, first 1) potential impacts are assessed, 2) a coordinated approach is developed with key external stakeholders, 3) local capacity for emergency response is assessed, and 4) stakeholder engagement is conducted. After the initial planning phase, the actual Emergency Preparedness and Response Plan is developed and adequate training is provided for all relevant stakeholders. Evaluation processes are carried out regularly and possible adjustments are implemented when seen fit.

Expected impact/goal of the practice: The expected impact of the practice is to prevent emergencies on site and to ensure that adequate processes to deal with occurring emergencies are in place.

Who is the target user group of the practice/intervention or implementing the practice/intervention? The target group of the guidance provided in this section are all site employees and contractors as well as the Social Performance and Security teams.

HYPERLINK View document

SOURCE

4D: Emergency Preparedness and Response Planning

YEAR 2021

DATA ITEM TYPE

Knowledge base

PRACTICE TYPE

Industry

FORMAT

Website

LEARNING RELEVANCE

Tool(kit)

COMMODITY

Unspecified (universally applicable)

EXTRACTIVE LIFE-CYCLE

Pre-exploration (land-use planning)
Exploration
Pre-exploitation / development stage (e.g. feasibility study)
Exploitation phase
Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)

SUSTAINABILITY SCOPE

Holistic risk management and emergency preparedness
Workers well-being

SYSTEM CHANGE POTENTIAL

improve workers well-being & safety
Emergency Preparedness and Response Plan

Figure 12: Good practice example on health and safety ([click here](#) to visit the example in the repository)

4.3.5 PERMITTING PROCESSES/POLICY INTEGRATION

Despite the need and urgency to optimise permitting processes of extraction sites and policy integration, these thematic areas are the least considered among the practices with 21% (76). Permitting is an administrative process where the company has to specify details of the future mineral extraction activity including infrastructure, operation design and post-extraction activities (i.e. post-closure land-use). All decisions taken at this stage are linked to geological and technological constraints and imply impacts on the environment and society, but also on economy (e.g. regional development). For this reason, the permitting process of an extraction site is crucial for introducing sustainable practices into mineral extraction operations. At this stage, it is necessary to ensure that both the extraction planning and post-extraction processes are responsible and sustainable, allowing the environment and the local community to benefit from the extraction of mineral resources. Policy integration addresses the question on how mineral policies and other policies related to the extractive sector are implemented and operationalised in European countries. This aspect influences the execution of the permitting process to a high degree.

This focus area highlights the pre-exploration phase, with 86% of the practices assigned at this life cycle stage (see Table 8). Permitting good practices are frequently linked to those in the focus areas of land use planning and impact assessment, as these three areas interact with each other. These practices deal with merging mineral exploration and mapping data with land use planning to provide approaches for mineral safeguarding, provision of data on mineral deposits, as well as ensuring data quality and the provision of and access to information to improve decision-making processes and policy-making (i.e. informing decision-makers in public authorities).

Table 8: Distribution of good practices on permitting/policy integration across the life cycle stages

SUMEX focus area	Number of practices	Life cycle stage	Number of practices
Permitting processes / policy integration	76	Pre-exploration (land-use planning)	65 (86%)
		Exploration	43 (57%)
		Pre-exploitation / development stage (e.g. feasibility study)	36 (47%)
		Exploitation phase	31 (41%)
		Post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	31 (41%)
		Assigned to all life cycle stages	25 (33%)

Since the permitting process covers all life cycle stages of an extraction site, good practices are relevant throughout all phases. Following, further research needs to be done to fill the gap and provide sufficient good practice examples across the entire extractive life cycle. Besides the permitting of new extraction sites, the expansion of already existing sites is a major topic in this focus area. Both areas involve numerous factors and conflict potentials, due to competing land uses, environmental protection versus mineral extraction, or social concerns about the extractive sector (i.e. social acceptance). In many European countries, the permitting process is split between different authorities that cover different areas, and is poorly or not coordinated to each other. As a result, the process is often ineffective and time-consuming. Moreover, the permitting of extraction sites can also be politically influenced, especially when policy-makers are pressured by other actors.

The good practice example demonstrated (Figure 13) aims at an effective and time-efficient licensing integration, focusing on political independence (i.e. assessment of environmental and ecological impacts based on higher-level considerations of the planning authorities), the expertise of the implementing authorities, and the management of the post-extraction landscape in the context of environmental and social aspects (i.e. ecology, and affected communities and employees).

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EFFECTIVE AND TIME-EFFICIENT PERMITTING AND LICENSING INTEGRATION (IRELAND)

- Health and safety ▶
- Land-use planning ▶
- Permitting processes / policy integration ▶
- Reporting official statistics ▶
- Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments ▶

Challenge the practice is addressing: Ireland was one of the largest producers of lead and zinc in the world. At the time of preparing the case study, an application to re-open the Galmoy mine was being considered. This case study regards the life-cycle of lead and zinc mines from exploration to closure and remediation. Irish mines are often located in rural areas and there is no right to carry out drilling for exploration activities in urbanised areas. There is currently one operating lead and zinc mine in Ireland along with other mines where other resources are extracted. To date, no mining project was ever refused planning permission in Ireland, although some associated infrastructure was refused planning permission to environmental considerations. Licensing and permitting for exploration and development is broadly split amongst three authorities, each dealing with one or more aspects.

Concrete practice to achieve the expected goal: 1) Independent Role of the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA): Its independence allows to reduce potential societal pressures and ensures that environmental and ecological impacts remain the overarching considerations of the permitting process. 2) Permits assessed by the most qualified authority to ensure adequate assessment of all aspects: Three separate permits are required to develop a mine, so each aspect is assessed by the most qualified/ appropriate body with relevant expertise in the subject. 3) Compulsory 'Closure, Restoration and Aftercare Management' Plans (CRAMP): It includes dynamic bonds paid to the State which can only be used for rehabilitation of the mine site post operations.

Expected impact/goal of the practice: 1) An agency

HYPERLINK View document

SOURCE

MINLAND: Mineral resources in sustainable land-use planning / D6.2: Final Manual for Good Practice Guidance

YEAR 2019

DATA ITEM TYPE

Knowledge base

PRACTICE TYPE

Public policy

FORMAT

Report / document

LEARNING RELEVANCE

Case study

COMMODITY

Unspecified (universally applicable)

SUSTAINABILITY SCOPE

Land-use and biodiversity

SYSTEM CHANGE POTENTIAL

three separate procedures for permitting ensure that the permission and licensing is done by the appropriate body with relevant expertise
Compulsory 'Closure, Restoration and Aftercare Management' Plans (CRAMP)

Figure 13: Good practice example on permitting/policy integration ([click here](#) for the full practice example)

5 SUMEX'S ROLE IN THE EU POLICY DEVELOPMENT

Environmental protection has become increasingly important in the European Union's policy. This development resulted in a **growing number and complexity of regulations, ranging from Natura 2000 to the Water Framework Directive and the Mining Waste Directive to carbon neutrality and circular economy aspirations**. For many of these policies on environmental protection and conservation of ecosystem services top-down policy instruments are applied by the European Union, meaning member states are responsible for the implementation of the policies themselves. According to this concept, the EU targets are the minimum to be reached, implying that the over-regulation of policies by the member states and the setting of higher standards is permissible. Owing to the diverse combination of EU policy objectives, numerous policy instruments at national level and diverging national mineral policy systems, **policy coherence across Europe and even within one country is challenging to achieve**. Therefore, the transposition of EU policies to national and further to regional and local levels may result in incoherency of policy objectives. This incoherency, as well as the over-regulation of European requirements, can affect and even inhibit industrial processes, including extraction activities.

Large-scale system transformations towards sustainability have the potential to alter prior pathway dependencies and entail a shift towards a better socio-economic system state. However, it needs to be kept in mind that the non-energy extractive sector is part of a larger system of production and consumption, influenced by many different actors. In such a complex system, no single actor or intervention has the authority, resources, or potential, respectively, to introduce a system change. A mix of disruptive or deep (e.g. change in attitude towards vulnerable groups and rights holders of land) and incremental or shallow interventions (e.g. reducing overall water pollution) targeting societally negotiated system goals (sustainable development overall or planetary boundaries for environmental matters).

Given this background, combined with the lack of exploration, also due to the easy availability of raw materials in a global market and the lack of social acceptance towards the extractive sector, **the extraction of mineral resources in Europe has declined**. Consequently, this led to a high dependence on imports to meet European's raw materials demand. The SUMEX project considers the transition to a **sustainably managed extractive sector as a key in addressing these challenges**. Efforts by the extractive sector to further improve its social and environmental performance are intended to promote extraction activities in Europe.

The identification of key topics affecting the extractive sector serves to represent areas requiring greater attention to facilitate the sector's sustainability transformation. The **demonstration of good sustainability practices from EU policy and industry (i.e. SUMEX knowledge repository) provides assistance to extractive companies in operationalising sustainable practices and to policy makers in EU member states to improve their mineral policy regimes**, in particular their permitting regimes and provides examples of what is already possible elsewhere. Despite the necessity of enhancing the permitting system, which is also highlighted by the Critical Raw Materials Act by the objective of reducing permitting durations for certain mineral raw materials, the SUMEX knowledge repository contains only a small number of good permitting practices.

SUMEX contributes to addressing relevant issues by promoting the sector's sustainability performance through the implementation of various measures such as **sharing information, training and demonstrating good practices**. Moreover, the project outputs are expected to support and facilitate the strengthening of the European extractive sector and thus assist to reach the objectives of the CRMA. The SUMEX Sustainability Framework serves as a roadmap to sustainable management in extractives by defining milestones, topics and goals and is supported by the good practice knowledge repository and training material, i.e. MOOC, podcast and briefing documents.

5.1 EUROPEAN REQUIREMENTS

To gain a deeper understanding of the European extractive sector, SUMEX examined two use cases in detail - Boliden Area in Sweden and Canteras La Ponderosa in Spain. The selection of the use cases resulted from the commodity type the project is concentrated on (i.e. construction and battery materials), due to the differences of the site and regulation characteristics (e.g. permitting and environmental protection), as well as from the location of the sites (i.e. southern and northern Europe), due to the differences in regulations. The reports '[Analytical Framework](#)' and '[Draft report policy analysis](#)' contain further information and insights on the case selection and results of analysis. Based on the two use cases, key topics influencing the extraction of mineral resources were identified: Environmental protection and competing land uses. With regard to environmental protection, the European Union directives on nature and biodiversity conservation, i.e. Natura 2000 and the Water Framework Directive (WFD) have a noteworthy impact on both cases. In contrast, competing land uses are more related to the divergent interests of actors and social needs.

Even though the **extraction of mineral raw materials has an impact on the environment and thus on ecosystem services**, their protection and extraction activities are not necessarily incompatible. The challenge is to **reconcile protecting the environment and preserving planetary boundaries with the extraction of mineral raw materials**. The European Union focuses on the concept of traditional environmental protection. This approach refers to the indirect use of resources and aims to reduce emissions to protect the natural environment from polluting hazards. Although the implementation of measures in the field of water and air protection or waste treatment has achieved some positive results, they have been less successful in the fields of nature, soil and landscape protection. The emission control approach subsequently imposes constraints on the regulation of other forms of use that are not inevitably associated with the generation of emissions, e.g. water abstraction or land-use conversion. In the context of natural resource management, traditional environmental policy is unable to provide a framework that enables and ensures sustainable use of resources while addressing the diverse and frequently conflicting uses of resources. The question of what sustainable use of natural resources, including mineral raw materials, means and how this can be translated and operationalised into measurable indicators and implementable policies is still being debated.

5.1.1 NATURA 2000

Extraction activities within Natura 2000 sites are often unwanted by various actors and might even be prevented, as mineral extraction is expected to harm biodiversity and ecosystem services. Biodiversity loss and decline of ecosystem services in Europe are frequently a consequence of changes in land uses (van der Sluis und Schmidt 2021). Natura 2000 sites are intended to protect certain species and habitats, and thereby counteract loss of biodiversity and degradation of ecosystem services. Due to industrial activities within Natura 2000, serious damage can be caused if not carried out in a responsible and sustainable manner, such as habitat loss and degradation resulting from land clearing, alteration of existing hydrological and hydrogeological systems, disturbance of existing local populations of species protected by EU directives, leading to their decrease and the promotion of colonisation by invasive species (European Union 2011). The Natura 2000 status of sites is used to regulate industrial activities, including mineral extraction, to protect species and habitats defined in these sites and to prevent adverse consequences. The European Commission published a guideline “Undertaking non-energy extractive activities in accordance with Natura 2000 requirements” (European Union 2011) to describe in more details the measures and conditions that are required to be met.

5.1.2 WATER FRAMEWORK DIRECTIVE (WFD)

The WFD aims to achieve a good status of all water bodies, both quantitative and qualitative. Based on the approved environmental quality standards, specifying what water quality has to be achieved by when, the WFD requires a management plan and an action program. The implementation of the WFD has made the access to water and water bodies increasingly difficult, which poses a challenge for industrial activities. The extractive industry frequently struggles to meet all approved environmental quality standards, because of natural factors such as geogenic contamination due to metal deposits or because of poor practices in the past. Exceedance of environmental quality standards due to geogenic contamination has the same implication for the WFD as water pollution caused by industrial activities. Subsequently, obtaining environmental permits for new extraction operations or the expansion of already existing operations is challenging. Water quality monitoring does not cover the whole water system, implying the origin of water pollution is often not known.

5.1.3 COMPETING LAND USES

Land-use conflicts between actors and extraction companies are mainly based on different land use interests. The requirement for land for extraction activities and their binding to deposits inevitably leads to competing land uses, especially in countries where limited land is available. Competing land uses between sectors or actors representing different interests cause tensions and trade-offs, mainly over land use planning and its orientation towards a particular type of use. This includes extraction activities and nature conservation (e.g. Natura 2000 or water protection areas), where extraction companies and government are in conflict with each other, since mineral extraction has frequently a low priority in land use planning in these areas. Land-use conflicts between extractive companies and civil society include rival claims; for instance, in northern Europe, there are conflicting land-uses between indigenous peoples and extraction activities, because of the need for land for reindeer husbandry.

5.1.4 TACKLING MAIN CHALLENGES OF THE EUROPEAN EXTRACTIVE SECTOR

The SUMEX Sustainability Framework contains a number of objectives and topics related to land-use and biodiversity, environmental protection, water management and the promotion of social acceptance, which are identified as the main challenges of the European extractive industry. These areas are also covered by the project's focus areas and following the knowledge repository provides a range of good practice examples to demonstrate both industry and policy-makers how these challenges can be managed (see chapter 4.2).

Social Acceptance

Social Acceptance is mainly covered by the focus area of socio-economic impact assessment. To promote the social acceptance towards mineral extraction, improving the sector's sustainability performance is crucial, with a focus on social, socio-economic (i.e. regional development) and environmental aspects. Another important element in this context is the awareness of the importance of mineral resources for our daily lives, as well as the understanding and insight into the processes of the extractive value chain itself and all factors behind. This refers to the conflict between environmental protection, land-use, etc. and the need for mineral raw materials. Both have a strong social necessity, but the consciousness for the need for mineral resources is frequently absent and additionally the mineral sector has a bad reputation, which is why it is rejected in some cases without reasoning. Therefore, education and training, as well as the provision of information, are not only essential at the government and industry level, but also for civil society. Through the public access to SUMEX project outputs, all actors equally have the opportunity to gain or improve their knowledge about sustainable management in the extractive sector. This ensures that also civil society is allowed to generate knowledge and awareness of the opportunities, limitations and challenges of the extractive sector in terms of sustainability. Thus, the SUMEX podcast and the MOOC are highly recommended for the civil society.

The industry's contribution to the promotion of social acceptance is the involvement of the community, for which there are various strategies and possibilities. Successful community involvement depends of course on the community, meaning the strategy has to be adapted accordingly. Nonetheless, there are some reference points which are given in the SUMEX framework and guidelines of other institutions (see knowledge repository). Practical examples that have been successful somewhere are presented in the knowledge repository.

Nature and Water Protection

Environmental impact assessment and reporting with a link to monitoring activities are the focus areas directly linked to nature and water protection. The protection of nature and water lies completely in the responsibility of the extractive companies, but also decision-makers should be aware of the impact of mineral extraction, how environmental pollution can be mitigated and about the possibilities of leaving a positive legacy. Apart from the environmentally sustainable extraction of mineral resources, the post-extraction phase of a mining site is a crucial factor when it comes to nature conservation. At this stage of the site life cycle, positive effects can be achieved that reduce or even completely balance the impacts of the extraction, e.g. restoration or even enhancement of biodiversity and ecosystem services. The good practice repository demonstrates a number of examples on how the post-extraction landscape can be planned and designed to achieve this.

While post-closure activities support the recovery of the land, impact assessment is needed to assess the effect of mineral extraction on the environment. This information is required for authorities and companies to know what measures are required to take to avoid any environmental degradation. Environmental impact assessment is also very widely covered in the knowledge repository, implying many companies have already successfully implemented strategies that can be used for the design and planning for new extraction sites.

Competing Land-uses

Effective land-use planning, a SUMEX focus area, is crucial to overcome conflicts regarding competing land-use. This issue is directly related to both the life cycle stage of an extraction site before the extraction starts and to the post-extraction stage. The permitting process is also highly impacted by competing land-use and is also a focus area of the project. To overcome this challenge, different factors have to be improved, including the enhancement of land-use planning, social acceptance and post-closure planning. All three areas require sharing of knowledge, implying the digital toolkit is a useful tool to support these targets. However, the good practices in the repository regarding land-use planning cover post-extraction land-use. Effective land-use planning strategies implemented by authorities are existing but rather rare.

5.2 EUROPEAN UNION'S RAW MATERIALS SUPPLY

In response to the increasing supply risk of certain mineral raw materials, i.e. critical raw materials, the European Union is facing, the European Commission has initiated the Critical Raw Materials Act (European Commission 2023a) to promote the sourcing of minerals from within the EU. The availability of CRMs is imperative for a variety of strategic sectors, such as digitalisation, net zero industry, aerospace and defence. In addition to the list of CRMs, the European Commission has identified several mineral raw materials crucial for Europe's green and digital transition technologies, defence and space, and are expected to pose supply risks in the future, i.e. strategic raw materials. Hence, the CRMA is intended to provide the EU with the necessary instruments to ensure its access to a secure supply of critical and strategic raw materials, as well as to enhance the EU's ability to monitor and reduce disruptive risks, and promote circular economy and sustainability in the European extractive sector.

Due to the comprehensive approach of SUMEX, the project outputs serve in different ways to contribute to the objectives of the CRMA and thus have the potential to enable the successful implementation of the Act in different ways. Even though the project focuses on the extractive value chain, its outputs also have a beneficial effect on the achievement of the Act's objectives that go beyond (i.e. recycling of CRMs or breakthrough technologies).

5.2.1 EU SOURCING OF MINERAL RESOURCES

The objective of the Act is to achieve the set benchmarks for domestic capacity and diversification of the EU sourcing of mineral raw materials across the strategic supply chain by 2030, which requires for EU annual consumption (i) a minimum of 10% to be extracted within the EU, (ii) a minimum of 40% to be processed within

the EU, and (iii) a minimum of 15% to be recycled within the EU, as well as (iv) a maximum of 65% of each strategic raw material from each relevant life cycle stage to originate from a single third country. For reaching these objectives, the European Union envisages a series of measures concerning the EU supply chain and the mitigation of supply risks, as well as research, innovation and skills, and the protection of the environment. These includes support to funding for selected strategic projects, strengthening the introduction and development of breakthrough technologies in CRMs, building a partnership of excellence on CRMs, recycling of CRMs from mineral waste and developing national exploration programmes for geological resources.

SUMEX RESPONSE

- **Sustainable management practices across the entire extractive value chain to promote raw materials extraction:** SUMEX considers sustainable management of the extractive sector as key to achieve the target of sourcing at least 10% of annual EU consumption from domestic sources. The **implementation of sustainable management practices** will not only be beneficial for **faster and higher approval in permitting processes, but will also facilitate social licence to operate (SLO)** in the actual operation and post-extractive uses.
- **Preventing negative impacts and enabling a positive legacy:** Improving the security and affordability of CRM supply needs to be accompanied by increased efforts to mitigate the negative impacts of mineral extraction, i.e. labour rights, human rights and environmental protection. The **SUMEX Sustainability Framework** identifies social, environmental and economic aspects that need to be considered throughout the **entire extractive value chain**, including descriptions of desirable sustainability-related target conditions, to ensure sustainable management.

5.2.2 EXTRACTIVE VALUE CHAIN & BEYOND

Extractive Value Chain

The initial step of strengthening and increasing the extraction of critical and strategic mineral raw materials within Europe, is the promotion of mineral exploration. Europe has great potential that has not yet exploited, among other reasons, due to the insufficient exploration of deposits. With the aim to combat this, the CRMA requires EU member states to develop national programmes for exploring geological resources. However, the implementation of extraction activities depends to a large extent on the permitting process of extraction sites, which takes in Europe on average seven to ten years. Permitting is a public authorisation process performed according to pre-set public procedures that vary among EU MS. Capacity, experience and expertise of MS varies substantially and is even different among regional authorities. The reduction of administrative burden is intended to simplify the permitting process for CRMs projects and thereby allow access to critical raw materials at an earlier stage. In addition, the CRMA envisages selected strategic project benefiting from support in terms of both reduced timeframes for permitting processes, i.e. 24 months for mining permits, and for access for finance.

SUMEX RESPONSE

Permitting has also been identified as one of the focus areas of the project, as it still has a strong need for improvement.

- **Improving the permitting process through the demonstration on good practices:** The **SUMEX knowledge repository** reveals permitting as the area with only a limited number of good practice examples, implying further research and greater attention needs to be paid to this topic. Nevertheless, the good practices contained in the data repository are intended to support industry and policy-makers in improving the permitting for new and the expansion of existing sites in order to foster mineral extraction in Europe.
- **Establish Permitting as an integrated policy process balancing extractive targets and environmental requirements:** SUMEX research identified several bottlenecks of the administrative permitting and licencing process. Extractive companies struggle to interpret environmental objectives (e.g. WFD environmental quality standards) and apply for new sustainable management practices that both satisfy the need for economically feasible extraction and high standard of nature protection. At the same time, absence of coordination and remit integration among public authorities for different policy objectives and requirements (water, biodiversity protection, infrastructure development, etc) complicates and lengthens the process which is then prone to unfavourable outcomes. Aggravating this starting position, public administration lacks the qualified personnel and sufficient resources to effectively assess permits against environmental requirements or state-of-the-art or new extractive (management) processes.
- **Permitting as holistic approach:** The **SUMEX Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)** addresses permitting as well as the other SUMEX focus areas, some of which are closely related to the permitting process (i.e. land-use planning and impact assessment). Bringing together different aspects and perspectives allows a holistic and comprehensive view on the permitting process, enabling it to be improved.
- **Both the demonstration of and learning from good practice** in the MOOC will provide **industry and decision-makers to gain a better understanding of the permitting process and the implications of it.** The purpose in doing this is to present the opportunities, but also the limitations, of both sides. In this way, mutual understanding can be established, which should subsequently lead to a **more effective permitting process.** Permitting should be a joint process between decision-makers and industry, as both sides have the same goal, i.e. promoting Europe's extraction activities.

Circularity – Beyond the Extractive Value Chain

In addition to the extraction of primary material, waste sites from active and historical operations are becoming increasingly relevant for the supply of CRMs. These sites have the potential to contain critical raw materials in quantities that are already reasonable to recover or will be in future. The CRMA's objective of circularity requires, alongside the rising recycling rates of CRMs, member states and private operators to investigate the potential for recovery from those sources.

SUMEX RESPONSE

Circularity has an important impact on the sector's sustainability performance, i.e. relieving the burden of primary resource extraction. A closing cycle does not only include the recycling of secondary raw materials, but also the extraction of minerals from tailings sites.

- **The SUMEX Sustainability Framework is relevant and applicable for both primary and secondary raw material sourcing:** It can serve as a roadmap for how the recovery of minerals from waste sites. Aspects to be considered in the extraction of primary sources apply equally to the extraction of raw materials from tailings.
- **Operationalisation and implementation of good practices:** The **SUMEX knowledge repository** also contains examples of good practice addressing circularity, which demonstrate decision-makers and industry what is already being done in this area and are intended to provide guidance for further development. These practices cover the recovery of tailings, as well as the recycling of secondary raw materials, planning beyond the mine life and after-use.

5.2.3 CAPACITY BUILDING

One of the pillars of the CRMA is building a large-scale competence partnership on CRMs and a Raw Materials Academy. The main objective is to enhance skills of professionals involved in critical raw materials supply chains in Europe. This includes various actors including public authorities, industries and civil society, meaning different backgrounds and expectations on the sector in terms of sustainability but also in general.

SUMEX RESPONSE

The introduction of a competence partnership and the implementation of a successful training concept requires the consideration of the different needs of the actors to be involved. It is crucial to ensure a common basis and understanding.

- **Easy to understand, but holistic sustainability frameworks with the potential to introduce system change:** The **SUMEX Sustainability Framework** can be used by decision-makers to get a holistic and future-oriented understanding of sustainable management in the extractives. It offers a **multi-actor based view** (validated with decision-makers from industry policy and civil society), **translates major societal challenges for the extractive sector** (e.g. water, planetary boundaries, fundamental rights of vulnerable groups etc), and is tied to actionable and practice-oriented solutions (i.e. applied and mapped for more than 300 European practices – see SUMEX knowledge repository).
- **Learning materials with practical solutions tied to scientifically based approaches with societal relevance:** The **SUMEX Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)** is here to orientate decision-makers on the most pressing issues and practical challenges faced by decision-makers, based on scientific materials and cutting-edge insights curated by renowned experts, and combines state of the art sustainability concepts with established and disruptive practices on the operational level.
- The **SUMEX Community of Practice (CoP)** provides a platform where information, knowledge and different opinions can be shared and exchanged, which foster cooperation between and understanding of the various actors involved in mineral extraction processes.

6 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The extraction of mineral raw materials within Europe is crucial to meet the European Union’s climate and policy targets, i.e. the European Green Deal, environmental regulations (e.g. Natura 2000, Water Framework Directive, or CO₂ regulations) and Critical Raw Materials Act. However, this demand for raw materials implies extraction to be done in a sustainable manner.

To achieve sustainable management in resource extraction, systemic changes are required, i.e. moving away from a purely profit-driven approach to one that facilitates and promotes the implementation and operationalisation of sustainable practices. The analyses presented above suggest **permitting, competing land uses and the balance between mineral extraction and protection of ecosystem services are the main challenges facing the European extractive industry**. Moreover, the **lack of social acceptance is an additional factor and constraint to the expansion of extraction activities in Europe**.

Building on the research that has been done in the course of the project, key points can be summarised that should be considered to facilitate the successful sustainability transition of the extractive sector. This requires measures on the part of industry, authorities and civil society.

1. Sustainability as dynamic approach

Our understanding of sustainability has changed a lot in recent decades. Hence, also sustainability for extractives should be seen as a dynamic concept, which is why authorities, industry and academia need to continue to develop it to avoid falling behind scientific developments and societal expectations. Thus, the SUMEX sustainability framework should be seen as dynamic and will need to be kept relevant and updated.

2. Just, inclusive and transformative system change

Sustainable management needs to focus more on transformative and multi-actor interventions. System change requires the evaluation of processes and the identification of transformation potentials. Both system changes with shallow LPs (incremental changes with little impact) and those with deep LPs (transformative and disruptive) are necessary. To realise transformations with deep LPs, companies, authorities and civil society have to collaborate.

Providing the necessary system changes to tangibly shift the extractive sector towards sustainability, this entails some of the following exemplary interventions:

- From a reporting perspective, industry actors to cover real change on site level, meaning they need to set specific targets for the full range of economic, social, and environmental impacts that even go beyond their operations, but also affect their suppliers or host communities. For example, in health and safety further emphasis needs to be on the operationalisation of shifting towards fundamental values like zero harm, ‘active care’ and people-centred approaches and the role it can play and impact it can have in the broader sustainability transition.

- In land use planning and extractive sector debates, the extractive sector needs to reflect on its role and position within these societal debates and which role it should play in the future: a) Provision of resources primarily needed for the renewable and zero-greenhouse gas emission system components, b) drastic reduction of land sealing (e.g. infrastructures) or impacts of land intensity; and c) what does sustainability and sustainability transformation mean for land uses with small spatial footprints. These approaches are not limited to the provision side, but must also target and incorporate the demand side and the need to significantly lower the mineral-resource-consumption on individual (behaviour-change) and societal level (societal change).
- From a policy and permitting perspective, interventions need to shift towards more transformative potential such as the possibility for alternative land use options to unfold in new permit applications (e.g. continuous site rehabilitation and onsite biodiversity areas), the possibility of extractive projects to take place in nature protected areas with restrictions not severely impacting the integrity of protected sites, or the possibility that extractive operations is or is not of greater public importance (overriding other conflicting goals such as nature conservation) when considering new permit applications.

3. Capacity building as key component

Knowledge is a crucial tool to enable progress. For this reason, open access to education and training on sustainable management in extractives for industry, authorities and civil society is important. Especially for companies and authorities, it is recommended to provide relevant employees both a broader knowledge on the extractive sector and its contribution to sustainability, as well as a detailed one on their field of tasks. SUMEX supports this by offering an open access digital toolkit (MOOC and knowledge repository), policy briefs and briefing documents on different topics and a podcast.

4. Exchange between all actors involved

The regular exchange between all actors involved allows the achievement of benefits and avoidance of conflicts. An active exchange enables a mutual understanding and building of trust, which following promotes the social acceptance. Additionally, active and open communication between extraction companies and authorities is meaningful to simplify and accelerate processes such as permitting, which benefits all parties. Therefore, it is necessary to establish an effective way for dialogue in all directions.

5. Policy implementation

When implementing EU policies at national, regional and local level, a uniform set of objectives is necessary to ensure the coherence of policies. This requires specialised authorities and sufficient capacity at country level. As especially small-size extraction companies often do not have the capacity for policy-trained professions, the provision of clear and understandable guidelines and support are desirable to enable those companies to comply with all requirements needed.

6. Land-use competition

Competing land-use is a major issue in Europe, often based on different expectations of various actors. To resolve this conflict, the collection of potential land-uses across Europe and within each country and the development of a long-term concept is recommended. This involves different actors and experts to ensure joint decisions and joint visions. In terms of the extraction of mineral raw materials, comprehensive exploration activities across Europe have to be done, as well as an evaluation where mineral extraction is necessary (i.e. strategic and critical raw material, short transport distances for construction materials). Post-closure land-use planning has to be included in this long-term planning, as well as the potential of multiple land-uses (e.g. combination of mineral processing and recycling plants).

7. Nature protection vs. exploration and extraction

Nature protection and mineral extraction activities are not mutually exclusive. Nevertheless, good planning to combine those fields is needed and requires the cooperation between extractive company, authorities and municipalities, as well as civil society. Extractive companies have to ensure a minimal impact on ecosystem services. This includes measures such as effective waste management, renewable energy production for their own needs, minimum energy and water consumption, or meaningful closure and revitalisation planning.

8. Permitting of new and extension of extraction sites

Many extraction companies struggle with the permitting process for a new site or the extension of an already existing one, due to different reasons. To improve the situation, measures on the part of the companies and/or authorities are needed:

- The permitting process differs between countries and even within a country. To simplify the permitting process for companies and implementing authorities, a transparent, standardised and uniform concept is needed, containing general framework conditions (i.e. aspects that have to be considered – e.g. SUMEX Sustainability Framework), defined requirements (i.e. factors that have to be fulfilled – e.g. legal requirements and impact assessment), and guidelines for specific cases (e.g. extraction activities in protected areas). Nevertheless, each site has to be considered individually due to different circumstances (e.g. national regulations, social and environmental requirements).
- To guarantee an efficient and less time-consuming permitting process, the availability of administrative capacity has to be ensured (i.e. sufficient workforce within member states to process proposals in a timely manner).
- Decision-makers, authorities and executing agencies, as well as companies has to be trained and educated accordingly to ensure a successful permitting process. This means authorities need to be familiar with the processes of extraction activities to be able to take meaningful decisions, as well as companies should be aware of the requirements and regulations to be fulfilled and how documents should be prepared.

9. Monitoring and reporting

Monitoring and reporting are necessary to document what has changed over time and in what way, meaning what impacts are caused by those changes. This concerns economic, environmental and social aspects. A regular and comprehensive review of extraction sites is required to ensure that they do not have negative consequences or to ensure prompt measures to address them. The public availability of data at a site level, including their interpretation by the company and/or authorities, is recommended. Auditing should also be done or at least confirmed by independent assessors.

SUMEX Project background

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC that started on 01.11.2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*SU*sustainable *M*anagement in *EX*tractive *I*ndustries) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration-to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify stakeholder learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all stakeholders.

More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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